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How working from home affects job satisfaction: Shedding light on the mechanisms[☆]

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ABSTRACT

As a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, a large number of people began working from home, and this form of work will remain important. However, there is no consensus on how working from home affects workers' job satisfaction. This paper provides novel insights into the mechanisms through which working from home affects job satisfaction. We use data from an online survey of graduates of professional colleges in Switzerland in 2021. We find that working from home increases job satisfaction on average. We then compare the relative importance of five mechanisms. We find that the positive association between working from home and job satisfaction is mainly due to increasing productivity and making work more interesting. Working from home is also positively associated with job satisfaction, but to a lesser degree, due to more flexible working hours. In contrast, our findings indicate that the worse work–life balance resulting from working from home and more difficult interactions with coworkers and supervisors are negatively associated with job satisfaction. We further find substantial heterogeneity in the relative relevance of these five mechanisms across workers with and without previous working from home experience, gender, age, and executive position. These differences might contribute to the lack of consensus on how working from home affects workers' job satisfaction.

1. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has led to a substantial rise in working from home, also called telework, telecommuting, remote work or hybrid work in the literature (Gottlieb et al., 2020). Although the concept of working from home was not new, the pandemic exposed more workers to this type of work arrangement and increased the intensity of exposure of workers already practicing this form of work (Barbour et al., 2021). This shift to working from home was especially notable among young people, and those in managerial, professional and related occupations (Brynjolfsson et al., 2020).

Working from home affects many aspects of life, such as mobility (Wöhner, 2022), physical health (Guler et al., 2021) and mental health (Oakman et al., 2020). Hence, the recent shift towards working from home has sparked a growing literature analyzing the effect of working from home on a variety of outcomes (Almeida et al., 2024). The literature examines measures of job satisfaction as well as measures

of psychological and mental health. However, the empirical literature on the effect of working from home on these outcomes remains limited (Lunde et al., 2022) and offers mixed results (Almeida et al., 2024; Crawford, 2022).

For instance, Yu and Wu (2021) find that a suitable home workspace of individuals a prerequisite for a positive effect of working from home on job satisfaction. Hackney et al. (2022) highlight the heterogeneity of the working from home effect across jobs, depending for example on the relevance of teamwork, job complexity and creativity. At the level of the firm, Song and Gao (2020) find that working from home decreases job satisfaction on average by increasing stress, while Bellmann and Hübler (2020) suggest that working from home increases job satisfaction in firms with strict contractual agreements.

These heterogenous effects might arise because working from home affects job satisfaction through several mechanisms. The existence of multiple mechanisms is supported by the multitude of affected outcomes suggested by the literature. For example, the literature suggests

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that working from home affects productivity and workload. Both of these outcomes represent potential mechanisms through which working from home could affect job satisfaction (Almeida et al., 2024). However, few papers analyze potential mechanisms through which working from home affects job satisfaction simultaneously (Ipsen et al., 2021).

Therefore, this paper fills this gap by comparing the relative importance of five mechanisms through which working from home may affect job satisfaction. Estimating the relative importance of these mechanisms is particularly challenging because it requires analyzing the effect of working from home on job characteristics, e.g. work–life balance, productivity, as well as the effect of the job characteristics on job satisfaction.

Building on the Job Demands–Resources model (JD–R model) and the Self-Determination Theory (SDT) (Russo et al., 2024), we analyze five mechanisms through which working from home affects job satisfaction. Working from home decreases job satisfaction through two of these five mechanisms. First, we hypothesize that working from home increases job demands and worsens the work–life balance. Second, working from home further challenges the ability to meet the need for relatedness by making interactions with colleagues and superiors more difficult.

Conversely, working from home increases job satisfaction through three of the five mechanisms. The third mechanism is that working from home makes work more interesting by allowing workers to focus on interesting tasks. Fourth, working from home also provides job resources by making work arrangements more flexible. Fifth, working from home increases productivity.

We estimate the relative importance of these five mechanisms using a survey of graduates of professional education and training (PET) colleges in Switzerland in 2021. We have information about the impact of working from home on job satisfaction. We also ask about the impact of working from home on work–life balance, working time flexibility, the interestingness of work, interactions with colleagues and superiors, as well as productivity. The combination of this information enables us to compare the relative importance of the mechanisms by which working from home affects job satisfaction.

In line with our hypotheses, our results suggest that working from home is positively associated with workers' job satisfaction through the following mechanisms: increased work productivity, more interesting work and flexible forms of work are positive. In contrast, our findings indicate that the worse work–life balance resulting from working from home and more difficult interactions with colleagues and supervisors are negatively related to job satisfaction.

We analyze how the effect of working from home depends on whether the intensity of working from home remained the same between 2019, before the pandemic started, and 2020, when many workers were forced to work from home due to actions taken in response to COVID-19. Employees with constant working from home intensity display a substantially smaller effect on job satisfaction than employees whose working from home intensity increased. The main explanations for this difference are the lower magnitude of the mechanisms of making work more interesting and increasing productivity. At the same time, the negative mechanism of worsening work–life balance also diminishes in magnitude. These findings might suggest that the long-term effects of working from home might be less beneficial than short-term effects.

We further conduct subsample analyses that compare men and women, non-executives and executives as well as young and old workers. The results suggest that the relative importance of the analyzed mechanisms differs substantially across subsamples. For example, we find that the productivity mechanism is more important for men, non-executives and older workers. Furthermore, the mechanism of making work more interesting is particularly important for non-executives and younger workers. The mechanism of deteriorating work–life balance is more pronounced among non-executives.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature and describes the five mechanisms. Section 3 explains the estimation strategy while Section 4 describes the dataset. Section 5 presents the results and discusses the heterogeneity across workers. Section 6 concludes and discusses potential implications for future research.

2. Literature review

The growing literature on the relationship between working from home and workers' job satisfaction offers mixed results. For instance, Song and Gao (2020) find in a recent study that working from home is associated with less job satisfaction mainly due to an increased level of stress. In contrast, Bellmann and Hübler (2020) suggest that working from home increases job satisfaction when it is based on strict contractual agreements. Yu and Wu (2021) further stress the importance of a suitable home workspace as a prerequisite for a fruitful perception of working from home.

Thus far, few papers systematically identify and assess the multiple mechanisms through which working from home affects job satisfaction. An exception is the work of Ipsen et al. (2021), who investigate workers' experiences of working from home during the COVID-19 pandemic and identify the main advantages and disadvantages of working from home. Their analyses suggest that an improvement of the work–life balance, an increase in work efficiency as well as greater work control are the main advantages of working from home. Constraints, work uncertainties and inadequate tools represent the main disadvantages. Nevertheless, Ipsen et al.'s analysis is restricted to identifying these characteristics and describing them rather than quantifying their effect.

Another related paper is by Kitagawa et al. (2021) who analyze the impact of working from home on mental health. They find that working from home increases mental health by facilitating greater focus on work, improving IT skills, reducing commuting time, decreasing fatigue and improving health, as well as by increasing exercising, having extra time for sleep and rest, and improving family relationships.

However, the literature provides little guidance regarding the relative magnitude of the mechanisms through which working from home affects job satisfaction in a comprehensive framework. To fill this gap, this paper decomposes the effects of working from home on workers' job satisfaction into different mechanisms and assesses their importance relative to one another. A mechanism describes the effect of working from home on job satisfaction via a change in a specific job characteristic.

To understand the mechanisms through which working from home affects workers' job satisfaction, we build upon the JD–R model (Bakker et al., 2023; Demerouti et al., 2001). This model originates in the burnout literature, but has been applied widely, including to the study of working from home (Galanti et al., 2021; Jamal et al., 2021; Junça Silva et al., 2024; Shamsi et al., 2021). The JD–R model suggests that job demands and resources affect job satisfaction. Job demands refer to those physical, social, or organizational aspects of the job that require sustained physical and/or psychological (i.e., cognitive and emotional) effort on the part of the employee, and are therefore associated with certain physiological and/or psychological costs (Demerouti et al., 2001). On the other hand, job resources are defined as those physical, psychological, social, or organizational aspects of the job that may (a) reduce job demands and the associated physiological and psychological costs, (b) be functional in achieving work goals, and (c) stimulate personal growth, learning, and development (Demerouti et al., 2001).

The SDT (Deci et al., 2017; Deci & Ryan, 2012) is another model that has been widely used to conceptualize the effects of working from home, for example on performance (Tudu & Singh, 2023), job satisfaction (Brunelle & Fortin, 2021), well-being (Šakan et al., 2020; Schade et al., 2021) and state of mind (Camilleri, 2021). SDT suggests

Fig. 1. Summary of the mechanisms.

that job satisfaction depends on autonomy, the feeling of competence and relatedness, the feeling of connectedness (Deci et al., 2017).

Russo et al. (2024) combines the JD–R model with the SDT in the integrated job demands–resources and self-determination model. Fig. 1 builds on the integrated job demands–resources and self-determination model. The figure shows that this paper investigates five mechanisms through changes in job demands, job resources, the need for autonomy, the need for relatedness and productivity.

Our first mechanism hypothesizes based on the JD–R model that working from home increases job demands. Existing evidence suggests that working from home worsens work–life balance (e.g. Bellmann & Hübler, 2020; Dettmers et al., 2016) by increasing workload and stress (e.g. Kunze et al., 2020; Wu & Chen, 2020; Barbieri et al., 2021). Furthermore, working from home blurs the boundaries between work and private life (Delanoëje et al., 2019; Boswell & Olson-Buchanan, 2007; Pluut & Wonders, 2020).

The literature shows that a worse work–life balance negatively affects subjective job satisfaction (Gallie & Russell, 2009; Scandura & Lankau, 1997). Increasing job demands decrease job satisfaction (e.g. Singh et al., 2019; Thulin et al., 2019; Boswell & Olson-Buchanan, 2007). This leads to the following hypothesis regarding the mechanism of job demands:

M1: Working from home decreases job satisfaction by worsening the work–life balance.

The second mechanism refers to an increase in job resources of the JD–R model in the form of working time flexibility. Information technology has enabled workers to access information from home at any time. Thereby, working from home increases time flexibility (Chung & Van der Lippe, 2020; Gajendran & Harrison, 2007; Kelliher & Anderson, 2010). Flexible working hours in turn increase job satisfaction (Kelliher & Anderson, 2010; Raziq & Maulabakhsh, 2015) by increasing perceived autonomy and decreasing work–family conflict (Gajendran & Harrison, 2007).

This leads to the following hypothesis regarding this mechanism:

M2: Working from home increases job satisfaction by making forms of working more flexible.

The third mechanism relates to how interesting individuals perceive their work to be. Lund et al. (2020) show that tasks involving

knowledge updating, learning, and creative thinking exhibit high potential for remote execution, thereby offering opportunities to make work more interesting. Remote work can also increase the perceived interestingness of work by enabling employees to focus on tasks they do not usually perform in the office (Ipsen et al., 2021). This dimension is closely linked to the interestingness aspect of engagement within the JD–R model, where engagement is defined as a positive, fulfilling work-related state characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004).

The JD–R model posits that engagement depends on the availability of job resources such as autonomy, participation, and feedback (Demerouti et al., 2001). Similarly, SDT emphasizes the role of autonomy and competence as core psychological needs that promote intrinsic motivation and well-being (Deci et al., 2017). Empirical evidence suggests that working from home supports these needs by enhancing personal control over work tasks (Kitagawa et al., 2021). This leads to the following hypothesis regarding this mechanism:

M3: Working from home increases job satisfaction by making work more interesting.

The fourth mechanism captures the part of the SDT which suggests that job satisfaction depends on relatedness, the feeling of connectedness (Deci et al., 2017). Working from home reduces relatedness. Concretely, working from home makes interactions with coworkers and supervisors individuals more difficult and less frequent (Gajendran & Harrison, 2007; Lal et al., 2021; Nakrošienė et al., 2019). Emanuel et al. (2023) show that working from home also reduces digital interactions and feedback. This can even lead to social isolation (Golden et al., 2008; Morganson et al., 2010). A more difficult interaction with colleagues and superiors decreases in turn workers' job satisfaction (Pincus, 1986; Warr, 2003). Taken together, this evidence allows us to formulate the following hypothesis:

M4: Working from home decreases job satisfaction by worsening interaction with colleagues and superiors.

The fifth mechanism, productivity, captures the fact that working from home might increase workers' productivity. The literature review of Hackney et al. (2022) finds that non-mandatory working from home increases productivity. This finding is however nuanced by the findings of Atkin et al. (2023), who find that workers randomly allocated to

working from home are less productive than their peers in the office. Another possible factor explaining the positive relationship between working from home and job satisfaction is that working from home may facilitate unpaid overtime work. This, in turn, may be viewed by some employees as a form of investment in the expectation of higher pay or promotion. Song (2009) shows that this is especially in the case for well-educated managers and supervisors.

In contrast, recent literature tends to find negative effects of mandatory working from home on productivity, e.g. during COVID-19 (Yang et al., 2022; Emanuel & Harrington, 2023; Morikawa, 2022; Gibbs et al., 2023; Kitagawa et al., 2021). What we see in the post-pandemic period in many countries, including Switzerland, is a hybrid work schedule in which employees spend a mixture of days each week at home and days at work. Recent studies on this hybrid form show a generally neutral effect of working from home on productivity, which turns out to be positive especially for workers in managerial positions (Bloom et al., 2024).

As the focus of our study lies on PET workers, which often hold managerial positions (see Section 4), we follow the productivity enhancing argument and hypothesize a positive effect of working from home on job satisfaction over an increase in productivity. This leads to the following hypothesis regarding this mechanism:

M5: Working from home increases job satisfaction by increasing productivity.

In the analyses, while looking at the long-term perspective of working from home, we will distinguish between workers who voluntarily worked from home before the pandemic and those who were forced or took the opportunity to work from home in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. This distinction will allow us to refine these hypotheses and observe whether the effect differs among the group of workers who were partially forced to work from home.

3. Empirical strategy

This section discusses our empirical strategy to analyze the relative relevance of the mechanisms through which working from home affects workers' job satisfaction. As measuring job characteristics such as work-life balance and productivity represents an empirical challenge, we follow the methodology of Bolli and Pusterla (2022) to estimate a reduced form model in which we directly ask respondents about the impact of working from home on job characteristics and job satisfaction. Concretely, we ask workers how strongly working from home affects their job satisfaction on a five-point Likert scale. Furthermore, we also ask workers to assess the impact of working from home on the corresponding job characteristic c . We then relate the impact of working from home on job characteristics and job satisfaction statistically. This methodology has the advantage that it does not require measuring job characteristics. We thus estimate the following equation via OLS:

$$\tilde{\omega}_i = \sum_{c=1}^5 \beta_c \tilde{\theta}_{ci} + \gamma \tilde{X}_i + \epsilon_i \quad (1)$$

ω_i represents the impact of working from home on job satisfaction for individual i . θ_c is the impact of working from home on job characteristic c . $\beta_c \theta_c$ represents the impact of working from home on job satisfaction through job characteristic c . X_i is a vector of other characteristics of workers that might affect job satisfaction. This control vector includes the following worker characteristics: *age*, *age*², *gender*, a dummy for an executive position, eight dummies for the field of study, and 13 dummies for the industry. Since ω_i , θ_c , and X_i are measured by asking respondents directly, we indicate this by using the superscript tilde.

$\hat{\beta}_c$ represents the effect of job characteristic c on job satisfaction. One possibility to assess the relative relevance of different job characteristics through which working from home affects job satisfaction

consists of multiplying the estimated $\hat{\beta}_c$ with the corresponding $\tilde{\theta}_c$. However, while the calculation of $\hat{\beta}_c \tilde{\theta}_c$ is straightforward, the magnitude of the resulting term is not easy to interpret. Another possibility consists of interpreting the explanatory power of each regressor as its importance. This measure is easier to interpret.

We measure the explanatory power of each regressor by the Shapley value (Shapley, 1953). The Shapley value shows the contribution of each variable to the goodness-of-fit of a statistical model. For illustration, assume an estimation model with k explanatory variables (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k). To understand the contribution of a variable, we need to estimate all possible models derived from the permutation of the regressors (Huettner et al., 2012). Mathematically, to calculate the contribution of a given regressor j we need to estimate the same number of models as the number of permutations ($K!$) of k regressors:

$$R_j^2 = \frac{1}{K!} R^2(f(x_j^\mu, x_j)) - R^2(f(x_j^\mu)) \quad (2)$$

where μ maps all $K!$ variable permutations. To obtain the Shapley value, we subtract the R^2 of the model that does not include x_j from the R^2 of the model that includes x_j and all regressors preceding x_j in the particular order x_j^μ . The Shapley value results as the average change in the R^2 over all permutations.

4. Data and variable description

This paper uses Swiss data from the ODEC Salary Survey 2021 covering a total of 1993 PET graduates. PET colleges award a formal vocational tertiary education certificate at level 6 of the ISCED-2011 classification.

Table 1 shows the summary statistics of variables used in the estimation. The dependent variable measures the influence of working from home on job satisfaction on a five-point Likert scale (-2 = "less satisfied"; 0 = "no change"; 2 = "more satisfied"). The mean of 0.33 suggests that working from home on average increases job satisfaction. This weakly positive overall effect is supported by 43% of respondents reporting a higher level of job satisfaction induced by working from home, in contrast to only 24% reporting a lower level of job satisfaction. The remaining 31% reported no change in job satisfaction as a result of working from home. This persistent positive effect of working from home on workers' job satisfaction is in line with previous findings in the literature (see, e.g., Bellmann & Hübler, 2020; Yu & Wu, 2021) but needs cautious interpretation, because it is specific to the subsample of workers with a PET college diploma examined in this paper.

Breakdowns of the dependent variable by gender, age, and executive position (see last row in Tables A.1–A.3 in the Appendix) yield values above 0, suggesting an overall positive effect of working from home on job satisfaction. Nevertheless, some small differences are noteworthy. Women report a greater positive effect of working from home on job satisfaction than men do. Also, workers without an executive position report slightly larger positive effects than those with executive positions. Finally, we observe no significant differences across age groups.

The main explanatory variables capture to what extent respondents agree with statements about the impact of working from home on the five job characteristics through which we expect that working from home affects job satisfaction. These variables are measured on a five-point Likert scale (1 = "I don't agree at all"; 5 = "I fully agree"). The results suggest that the strongest effect of working from home lies in more flexible forms of working time (4.21), followed by a worsening of interactions with colleagues and superiors (3.93), and an increase in productivity (3.49). Smaller effects occur in terms of making work more interesting (2.78) and worsening work-life balance (2.73).

If working from home affects a given job characteristic only slightly, it will only moderately affect job satisfaction through this characteristic. Therefore, these results cast doubt on the mechanisms M1 and M3. Note that these two low values do not necessarily mean that the work-life balance and the interestingness of work have no effect on job

Table 1
Variables description.

	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max
DEPENDENT VARIABLE					
Working from home (wfh) affect my job satisfaction	1993	0.32	1.14	-2	2
MAIN EXPLANATORY VARIABLES					
M1: working from home worsens the work–life balance	1993	2.73	1.34	1	5
M2: working from home enables more flexible forms of working time	1993	4.21	0.98	1	5
M3: working from home makes my work more interesting	1993	2.78	1.16	1	5
M4: working from home worsens interaction with colleagues and superiors	1993	3.93	1.06	1	5
M5: working from home increases my productivity	1993	3.49	1.16	1	5
OTHER VARIABLES					
Age	1993	36.99	9.47	21	68
Women	1993	0.23		0	1
Executive position	1993	0.42		0	1
Field of study					
Agronomy	1993	0.07		0	1
Catering	1993	0.02		0	1
Health	1993	0.00		0	1
Arts	1993	0.01		0	1
Social work and adult education	1993	0.02		0	1
Technology	1993	0.56		0	1
Business administration	1993	0.30		0	1
Industry					
Transportation	1993	0.00		0	1
Construction	1993	0.08		0	1
Financial and insurance activities	1993	0.09		0	1
Professional, scientific and technical activities	1993	0.05		0	1
Other service activities	1993	0.01		0	1
Administrative and support service activities	1993	0.07		0	1
Education	1993	0.03		0	1
Accommodation and food service activities	1993	0.06		0	1
Human health and social work activities	1993	0.06		0	1
Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motorvehicles and motorcycles	1993	0.03		0	1
Information and communication	1993	0.10		0	1
Manufacturing	1993	0.30		0	1
Transportation and storage	1993	0.05		0	1
Public administration and defence; compulsory social security	1993	0.07		0	1
Intensified working from home in 2020 compared to 2019 (e.g., due to COVID-19)	1993	0.93		0	1

satisfaction. Instead, they mean that working from home does not affect them strongly.

The bottom part of Table 1 shows summary statistics of control variables. These summary statistics reveal that most respondents are male, between ages 21 and 68, with an average age of 37 years. About 37% of respondents hold executive positions. Executive positions include positions on the board of directors and management. About half of respondents studied a technical field, followed by business administration with about one third of respondents. The remaining respondents are subdivided among the other five study fields. In terms of the industry in which they work, more than a quarter of respondents are employed in manufacturing. Workers in information and communication, finance and insurance, and construction are also relatively common. Finally, Table 1 shows in the last row that 93% of respondents worked from home more in 2020 than in 2019, while 7% worked from home in 2020 less or to a similar extent as before the start of the COVID-19 pandemic. This information will be used to construct a subsample of workers who are already accustomed to working from home, which will be presented as a supplement to the main results for the full sample.

A comparison between these summary statistics and the values collected by the Swiss Federal Statistical Office (FSO) through the Survey on Professional Education¹ suggests that our sample is not completely representative of the specific subgroup of workers with a degree from a PET college. Concretely, our sample overrepresents men and graduates in technical fields. Nevertheless, the average age at graduation in our sample is in line with the ones reported by respondents is close to the one reported by the FSO.

¹ <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/en/home/statistics/education-science/diploma/tertiary-professional-education/colleges-higher-education-diploma.html>

5. Estimation results

5.1. Main results

The first two columns of Table 2 show the estimation results of the reduced-form model presented in Eq. (1). In column (3), we report the average effect of working from home on job characteristics ($\hat{\theta}_c$), while in column (4) we multiply it with the estimated coefficients ($\hat{\beta}_c \hat{\theta}_c$). Finally, in column (5) we show the Shapley values, which describe the contribution of each regressor to the goodness-of-fit of the estimation in column (2).

The estimations in the first two columns differ in terms of control variables, e.g., column (1) contains no control variables. Overall, the five characteristics explain about 44.7% of the total variance in the effect of working from home on job satisfaction. Column (2) controls for workers' individual characteristics. We find that these control variables have hardly any influence on the estimated coefficients. While the additional control variables increase the percentage of explained variance, they do so only slightly, to 45.8%.

The coefficients of the OLS regression of column (2) test the association through the mechanisms. The value for $\hat{\beta}_c \hat{\theta}_c$ reported in column (4) and the Shapley values reported in column (5) allow us to compare the importance of the mechanisms.

We start by considering the work–life balance mechanism. The OLS coefficient for work–life balance is negative and statistically significant. This negative sign suggests that a worsening of work–life balance resulting from working from home decreases job satisfaction. Column (3) reports the corresponding value of $\hat{\theta}_c$, the impact of working from home on work–life balance, which is below average. Thus, as column (4) shows, $\hat{\beta}_c \hat{\theta}_c$ amounts to 0.48. Column (5) shows that the worsening of work–life balance due to working from home accounts for about

Table 2
Main results.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Dependent variable: effect of working from home on job satisfaction	$\hat{\beta}_c$	$\hat{\beta}_c$	$\tilde{\theta}_c$	$\hat{\beta}_c \tilde{\theta}_c$	Percentage of explained variation
M1: Working from home worsens the work–life balance	−0.180*** (0.0152)	−0.177*** (0.0152)	2.73	−0.48	7.3%
M2: Working from home enables more flexible forms of working time	0.129*** (0.0199)	0.126*** (0.0199)	4.21	0.53	3.7%
M3: Working from home makes my work more interesting	0.229*** (0.0193)	0.225*** (0.0194)	2.78	0.63	11.9%
M4: Working from home complicates interaction with colleagues and superiors	−0.175*** (0.0198)	−0.175*** (0.0198)	3.93	−0.69	6.6%
M5: Working from home increases my productivity	0.285*** (0.0193)	0.286*** (0.0196)	3.49	1.00	13.8%
Worker Individual Characteristics, Study Field, and Industry	No	Yes			1.9%
<i>N</i>	1993	1993			
<i>R</i> ²	0.447	0.458			

Notes: Columns (1) and (2) reports the results of the OLS regression having as dependent variable the effect of working from home on job satisfaction, which is measured on a five point Likert scale (−2 = “less satisfied”, 0 = “no change”, 2 = “more satisfied”). Robust standard errors in parentheses. Worker characteristics is a vector of control variables as described in Table 1 plus industry dummies according to 1-digit NACE Rev. 2 classification. Column (3) shows $\tilde{\theta}_c$, the average effect of working from home on job characteristics as reported in Table 1. Column (4) multiplies the $\hat{\beta}_c$ from column (2) with the $\tilde{\theta}_c$ from column (3). Column (5) reports the Shapley values, which describe the absolute contribution of each regressor in the goodness-of-fit of the estimation in column (2). * p < 0.10, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01.

7.3% of the total variance. This finding implies that working from home is associated with job satisfaction through mechanism M1, which suggests that the worsening of work–life balance by working from home is negatively associated with job satisfaction.

The second mechanism is the working-time flexibility. The OLS coefficient for this mechanism is positive and statistically significant but relatively small. However, given the high value of $\tilde{\theta}_c$, the resulting value of $\hat{\beta}_c \tilde{\theta}_c$ is relatively large 0.53. This indicator explains about 3.7% of the total variance. This finding implies that working from home is associated with job satisfaction through mechanism M2, suggesting that the allowance of more flexible forms of work are positively associated with job satisfaction.

The OLS coefficient for the mechanism through interestingness of work is positive and statistically significant. Although $\tilde{\theta}_c$ is relatively low, the resulting $\hat{\beta}_c \tilde{\theta}_c$ is relatively high (0.63). This mechanism explains about 11.9% of the total variance. Our estimations thus imply that working from home is associated with job satisfaction through mechanism M3, suggesting that an increase in work interestingness derived from working from home is positively associated with job satisfaction.

The fourth mechanism accounts for interactions with other individuals. The OLS coefficient for the interaction with colleagues and superiors is negative and statistically significant. Given the relatively high value of $\tilde{\theta}_c$, the resulting $\hat{\beta}_c \tilde{\theta}_c$ is also relatively high and negative (−0.69). This mechanism explains about 6.6% of the overall variance, meaning that the worse interaction with colleagues and superiors due to working from home is negatively associated with job satisfaction, and thus supports the association through mechanism M4.

The fifth mechanism is productivity. The large and positive OLS coefficient suggests that this mechanism has the strongest effect on job satisfaction. Furthermore, this mechanism has the largest value of $\tilde{\theta}_c$, meaning that working from home affects workers’ productivity relatively strongly. The combination of the two large values for $\hat{\beta}_c \tilde{\theta}_c$ gives a very high value (1.00), showing the large contribution of this mechanism to explaining the effect of working from home on job satisfaction. Indeed, this mechanism accounts for about 13.8% of the total variance. This result clearly supports the association through mechanism M5, namely that an increase in productivity derived from working from home is positively associated with job satisfaction.

Fig. 2 reports the main results of the paper by graphically summarizing the relative importance of the mechanisms.

5.2. Heterogeneity across workers’ characteristics

This section discusses the heterogeneity across four characteristics of workers: gender, age and executive position. We start by discussing some potential reasons for heterogeneity across workers, though developing formal hypotheses in these regards remains beyond the scope of this paper.

Gender

Women continue to bear a disproportionate share of caregiving and domestic responsibilities (Craig & Churchill, 2021; Shockley et al., 2021). These responsibilities can lead to work–family conflict (Gajendran & Harrison, 2007). Hence, mechanisms related to work–life balance and flexible working time may have a greater impact on women’s job satisfaction compared to men’s (Castro-Trancón et al., 2024; Chung & Van der Lippe, 2020; Magnier-Watanabe et al., 2023; Scandura & Lankau, 1997). Additionally, women tend to report a stronger need for social belonging in the workplace (Morrison, 2009), suggesting that the mechanism related to social interaction may also be stronger for women. At the same time, women tend to experience more unscheduled interruptions and are more likely to multitask during remote work (Barbero et al., 2023; Gibbs et al., 2023). In contrast, men appear to benefit more from autonomy when working from home (Reuschke, 2019). Accordingly, mechanisms linked to productivity and the interestingness of work may contribute more strongly to job satisfaction for men than for women (Magnier-Watanabe et al., 2023).

Executives vs non-executives

Executives typically enjoy substantial autonomy over their tasks, schedules, and work boundaries (Kelliher & Anderson, 2010). As a result, working from home may offer fewer additional autonomy-related benefits to executives, implying that the mechanisms of work–life balance (Pluut & Wonders, 2020), interestingness of work (Deci et al., 2017) and productivity could be more influential for non-executives. Conversely, the preexisting autonomy of executives may enhance the positive effects of working time flexibility when working remotely. Finally, because executive roles depend heavily on interpersonal communication for leadership, supervision, and decision-making, the negative mechanism of impaired interaction may be more pronounced among executives than among non-executives (Emanuel et al., 2023; Golden et al., 2008).

Fig. 2. Illustration of the main results.

Notes: This figure shows the relative importance of five mechanisms in explaining the impact of working from home on workers' job satisfaction. The width of the arrows represents the relative importance of the mechanism. Red stands for mechanisms with negative effects on job satisfaction, while green represents a positive effect.

Table 3

Expected group differences (effective ones are in bold) across mechanisms linking working from home and job satisfaction.

Worker characteristic	Work–life Balance (M1)	Working Time Flexibility (M2)	Interestingness of Work (M3)	Interaction (M4)	Productivity (M5)
Effect stronger for...					
Gender	...women	...women	...men	...women	...men
Executive position	...non-executives	...executives	...non-executives	...executives	...non-executives
Age	...younger	...younger	...younger	...younger	...older

Table 4

Mean comparison of worker subgroups either accustomed to working from home or not.

DEPENDENT VARIABLE	Worked already from home in 2019		Worked from home more in 2020 than in 2019		Difference	
	mean	sd	mean	sd	δ	t
Working from home affects my job satisfaction	0.10	0.86	0.33	1.16	-0.24 **	(-3.09)
MAIN EXPLANATORY VARIABLES						
Working from home worsens the work–life balance	2.92	1.34	2.72	1.34	0.20	(1.76)
Working from home enables more flexible forms of working time	3.92	1.04	4.23	0.97	-0.31 ***	(-3.47)
Working from home makes my work more interesting	2.74	1.18	2.78	1.15	-0.04	(-0.36)
Working from home complicates interaction with colleagues and superiors	3.81	1.13	3.94	1.06	-0.13	(-1.32)
Working from home increases my productivity	3.17	1.24	3.51	1.15	-0.34 **	(-3.19)
N	143		1850		1993	

Notes: * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Age

There are several possible and meaningful differences between workers below and above the median age in our sample, which is 36. Younger workers often struggle more with maintaining boundaries between work and personal life (Becker et al., 2022; Scheibe et al., 2024), indicating that mechanisms related to work–life balance and flexible scheduling may play a greater role in their job satisfaction. Furthermore, older workers may have better boundaries, meaning that they may benefit more from productivity gains when working from home. Similarly, the productivity mechanism might be more important for older workers because they have a higher need for competence (Laguerre & Barnes-Farrell, 2025; Van den Broeck et al., 2016). However, limited digital fluency in this group can offset these advantages (König & Seifert, 2022; Lee et al., 2022). Moreover, younger workers place heightened importance on opportunities for learning (Lyons & Kuron, 2014), networking (Zacher, 2014), and social interaction (Barrero et al., 2023; Kirwan et al., 2024), suggesting that mechanisms related to interestingness of work and social connectedness may have stronger effects on job satisfaction for younger than for older workers.

Table 3 summarizes potential group differences across mechanisms based on the discussed literature. This table also previews in bold the group differences for which we found a difference in the Shapley values. Specifically, to investigate differences in the relevance of the five mechanisms according to worker characteristics, we proceeded as follows. We run the reduced-form model described in Eq. (1) for sub-samples of workers according to their individual characteristics. The results of these estimates for sub-samples according to respondents' gender, age, and executive position are reported in Tables A.1–A.3 in Appendix. To facilitate the comparison, Fig. 3 shows the Shapley values, which quantify the relative importance of each mechanism in the corresponding sub-sample of workers.

Looking first at heterogeneity by gender, Fig. 3(a) shows that the productivity and interestingness mechanisms are relatively more relevant for men than women. This finding is consistent with the literature suggesting that men profit more from these mechanisms because they benefit more from autonomy and experience less unscheduled interruptions and less multitasking. It is also worth noting that both mechanisms are the most relevant for both groups of workers. Furthermore,

Fig. 3. Contribution to R^2 across sub-samples.

Notes: This figure shows the percentage of variation explained by each channel across subgroups of workers. Tables A.1–A.3 in the Appendix reports the OLS estimates by workers’ characteristics, which underpin the regressors’ contribution to R^2 .

the expected larger relevance of working time flexibility for women due to more work–family conflict is also supported. In contrast, no larger effects were found for men in the mechanisms by which working

from home affects work–life balance. Furthermore, we find no evidence that a stronger need for social belonging among women increases the relevance of the mechanism of hindering interaction with colleagues or supervisors.

In terms of heterogeneity across executive positions, Fig. 3(b) shows that executives experience a greater deterioration in interactions with colleagues and superiors, which is expected based on the reason that executives depend more heavily on interpersonal communication. Executives also derive less value from increased productivity and work interest. These findings are in line with the reasoning that executives typically enjoy substantial autonomy already. Similarly, in line with the autonomy argument, the deterioration in work–life balance is more pronounced for non-executives, though only slightly. Finally, the improvement through working time flexibility is slightly more pronounced for executives, which is in line with the reason that preexisting autonomy enhances the positive effects of working time flexibility. However, the latter two differences are relatively small.

As for heterogeneity across age groups, Fig. 3(c) shows that the more interesting work mechanism benefits younger workers more. This finding is expected based on the argument that opportunities for learning, networking and social interaction are more important for younger workers. Also in line with the reasons that older workers have higher need for competence and struggle less with boundaries between work and personal life, we find that the increase in productivity plays a greater role for older workers. Hence, the lower digital fluency of older workers is offset by other factors in this regard. The worsening of work–life balance due to working from home has roughly the same impact on workers of all ages. The improvements through more flexible working hours, are higher for younger workers, though the difference is only small. Finally, contrary to our reasoning that opportunities for learning, networking and social interaction are more relevant for younger workers, we find that the mechanism of deteriorating interactions with colleagues or superiors is more relevant for older workers. This difference might arise because younger workers have higher digital fluency, making them more adept at using communication-enhancing technology (Golden et al., 2008).

5.3. Heterogeneity across prior telework experience

As previously mentioned, the COVID-19 pandemic caused many workers to work from home more (Gottlieb et al., 2020). Nonetheless, the concept of working from home was not entirely new, at least for some workers. This subsection explores how the effect of working from home on job satisfaction might vary depending on whether telework was a new phenomenon for workers or whether they had prior experience with it. We take advantage of the fact that the survey includes information on whether individuals changed their working from home intensity between the pre-pandemic period in 2019 and 2020.

Approximately 92% of the surveyed workers reported an increase in working from home between 2019 and 2020 (see Table 1). Therefore, roughly 8% of workers experienced a level of working from home similar to their previous experience. Working from home was also not a new phenomenon for them. These 185 workers provide a unique research opportunity to investigate potential changes in the effects of working from home (Hackney et al., 2022).

Table 4 compares the means of the dependent variable and the main explanatory variables between these two groups. The impact of working from home on job satisfaction, our dependent variable, is significantly lower for workers who maintained constant working from home intensity. This tentatively suggests that the positive effect of working from home might diminish in the long-term.

Analysis comparing the means of the main explanatory variables suggests that individuals with constant telework intensity assessed the negative effect of working from home on the work–life balance more strongly. They also evaluate a weaker advantage of working from home on productivity and the possibility to have more flexible forms of

Table 5
Results among subgroups of workers either accustomed to working from home or not.

Dependent variable: effect of working from home on job satisfaction	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
	Worked already from home in 2019				Worked from home more in 2020 than in 2019			
	$\hat{\beta}_c$	$\tilde{\theta}_c$	$\hat{\beta}_c \tilde{\theta}_c$	Percentage of explained variation	$\hat{\beta}_c$	$\tilde{\theta}_c$	$\hat{\beta}_c \tilde{\theta}_c$	Percentage of explained variation
M1: Working form home worsens the work–life balance	0.0346 (0.0509)	2.99	0.09	0.3%	-0.197*** (0.0157)	2.72	-0.54	9.1%
M2: Working form home enables more flexible forms of working time	0.0253 (0.0671)	3.95	0.12	0.4%	0.135*** (0.0204)	4.25	0.57	4.0%
M3: Working form home makes my work more interesting	0.119* (0.0688)	2.73	0.32	5.7%	0.220*** (0.0200)	2.79	0.61	12.1%
M4: Working form home complicates interaction with colleagues and superiors	-0.173*** (0.0614)	3.90	-0.72	7.1%	-0.150*** (0.0207)	3.92	-0.59	5.9%
M5: Working form home increases my productivity	0.144** (0.0633)	3.11	0.43	6.5%	0.318*** (0.0204)	3.50	1.11	15.8%
Controls	Yes			10.8%	Yes			1.6%
N	185				2225			
R ²	0.301				0.485			

Notes: Columns (1) and (5) reports the results of the OLS regression having as dependent variable the effect of working from home on job satisfaction, which is measured on a 5 point Likert scale (-2 = “less satisfied”, 0 = “no change”, 2 = “more satisfied”). Robust standard errors in parentheses. Worker characteristics is a vector of control variables as described in Table 1 plus industry dummies according to 1-digit NACE Rev. 2 classification. Columns (2) and (6) show $\tilde{\theta}_c$, the average effect of working from home on job characteristics as reported in Table 4. Columns (3) and (7) multiplies the $\hat{\beta}_c$ with the $\tilde{\theta}_c$ from columns (1) and (5) respectively. Columns (4) and (8) report the Shapley values, which describe the absolute contribution of each regressor in the goodness-of-fit of the estimation in column (1) and (5) respectively. * p < 0.10, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01.

working time. The means of the remaining two explanatory variables — the increase in the interestingness of work as well as the worsening of interaction with colleagues and superiors — show no statistically significant differences. These findings suggest that there is no difference between the impact of working from home in relation to these two job characteristics.

Table 5 displays the results for two subsamples of workers. Similar to the main results, we present the outcomes of the OLS regression for each subsample, alongside the values for $\tilde{\theta}_c$, which represents the subsample mean of the five mechanisms, and $\hat{\beta}_c \tilde{\theta}_c$, which is the product of the two previous columns. Finally, the Shapley values in the last column quantify the importance of each mechanism.

The results indicate that, for workers who have previous experience with teleworking, working from home is less beneficial in terms of job satisfaction than for those who are experiencing it for the first time. This difference mainly arises from a less positive impact on the interestingness of work and a much smaller increase in productivity. The findings on productivity contradict the evidence in the literature on mandatory versus non-mandatory use of telework, which suggests larger positive effects of non-mandatory work from home. The fact that our estimates show a smaller effect for workers accustomed to working from home can possibly be interpreted as indicating that the increase in productivity decreases in the long run. Alternatively, the finding might suggest that workers become better at estimating the productivity effects of working from home over time.

Furthermore, the beneficial impact through a more flexible work schedule is no longer statistically significant among the group of workers whose working from home intensity remained the same. However, the mechanism of worsening work–life balance might also become less important for workers with previous experience of working from home. The negative mechanism of worsening interaction with colleagues and superiors on the other hand remains similarly important.

The results just presented need to be interpreted with caution for two reasons. First, a relatively small sample of workers displayed a constant working from home intensity. Second, we might expect a self-selection effect. For example, workers with constant working from home intensity might have different prerequisites that allowed them to work from home before the pandemic. In contrast, the rest of the workers were — at least to some extent — forced to work from home more. Taking all of this into account, our results are thus only indicative

of possible differences in working from home in the short-term versus the long-term.

Finally, it is worth mentioning that the results for the sub-sample for which the intensity of working from home has increased remain qualitatively robust. The increase in working from home intensity was largely exogenously driven by the pandemic. Therefore, this robustness check helps to support a causal interpretation of our results.

6. Conclusion and limitations

This paper provides insights into the relative strength of five mechanisms through which working from home affects job satisfaction. The analysis is based on a survey among graduates of PET colleges in Switzerland. We find that working from home increases job satisfaction particularly by increasing work productivity and making work more interesting. Greater working time flexibility due to working from home also has a positive association with job satisfaction but to a lesser degree. Our results further suggest that the worsening work–life balance and interaction with colleagues and superiors resulting from working from home are negatively associated with workers’ job satisfaction.

These findings suggest that firms can improve productivity by allowing their workers to work from home. However, these positive effects differ across jobs, tasks and individuals (Hackney et al., 2022). Hence, firms should tailor the share of working from home to the situation at hand.

Decisions on the share of working from home should also consider the team and its dynamics. Limiting working from home to ensure in-person interactions can mitigate the negative effects of working from home through worsening interactions with colleagues and superiors. In addition, encouraging regular virtual interactions and providing suitable digital infrastructure can also help to preserve workplace cohesion (Emanuel et al., 2023; Golden et al., 2008).

Reaping the benefits of working from home through productivity and more interesting work requires an increase in the autonomy of workers (Deci et al., 2017). Hence, firms need to embrace cultural change to establish a working environment that fits working from home. This cultural change needs to go hand in hand with a shift in communication and management approaches. It further requires developing a digital infrastructure that enables working from home and managing more autonomous workers (Hackney et al., 2022).

The environment of the firm also moderates the negative side effects of working from home through deteriorating work–life balance. Providing clear boundaries between work and personal life through policies on availability and expectations can mitigate the negative effects of working from home through deteriorating work–life balance (Boswell & Olson-Buchanan, 2007).

One limitation of our study is the lack of an experimental or quasi-experimental identification strategy. We analyze several channels simultaneously. Furthermore, we control for observable characteristics such as gender, age, field of study, industry and executive position. However, other influences might affect job satisfaction. Examples include the availability of infrastructure and whether workers have children at home. Hence, the presented estimates are not necessarily causal.

An additional limitation is that we analyze five potential mechanisms only. It remains for future research to assess whether other mechanisms might play an important role as well. Furthermore, our sample of PET graduates is not perfectly representative. This is particularly true regarding education level, field of study and gender. Therefore, the external validity of our results needs to be treated with caution. Data for workers without tertiary vocational education might yield different results.

While we analyze heterogeneity across some worker characteristics, we are not able to account for other moderating factors identified in the literature. In particular, we have no information about support from management or family (Jamal et al., 2021) or the quality of the workspace at home (e.g. Allen et al., 2015; Magnier-Watanabe et al., 2023).

The self-assessment of working from home, job satisfaction and the effect of working from home on various job characteristics might entail measurement error. In addition, we lack information about the intensity of working from home. Furthermore, while our methodology allows us to compare the different mechanisms, we cannot interpret the impact of job characteristics in absolute terms. These limitations should be addressed in future research.

Despite these limitations, this paper presents first evidence on the relative importance of the channels through which working from home affects job satisfaction. Moreover, it offers a first analysis of how these effects may be differentiated depending on personal characteristics, job characteristics and whether people had previous telework experience.

Table A.1
Sub-sample results: Estimation by gender.

	Men				Women			
	(1) $\hat{\beta}_c$	(2) $\tilde{\theta}_c$	(3) $\hat{\beta}_c * \tilde{\theta}_c$	(4) Percentage of Explained Variation	(5) $\hat{\beta}_c$	(6) β_{OLS}	(7) $\hat{\beta}_c * \tilde{\theta}_c$	(8) Percentage of Explained Variation
M1: Working from home worsens the work–life balance	−.178*** (.0196)	2.72	−.49	7.91	−.179*** (.0344)	2.76	−.49	7.49
M2: Working from home enables more flexible forms of working time	.111*** (.0244)	4.16	.46	3.42	.203*** (.0477)	4.38	.88	4.86
M3: Working from home makes my work more interesting	.223*** (.0243)	2.79	.62	12.11	.244*** (.0468)	2.72	.66	11.27
M4: Working from home complicates interaction with colleagues and superiors	−.175*** (.0249)	3.92	−.69	6.71	−.165*** (.0452)	9.97	−.65	6.17
M5: Working from home increases my productivity	.295*** (.0239)	3.47	1.02	14.36	.233*** (.0487)	3.53	.82	11.18
Worker characteristics	Yes			2.38	Yes			5.03
N	1538				455			
R ² (%)	46.91				46.01			
Mean of dependent variable	0.30				0.38			

Notes: Columns (1) and (5) report the results of the OLS regression having as dependent variable the effect of working from home on job satisfaction, which is measured on a Likert scale (−2=“less satisfied”, 0=“no change”, 2=“more satisfied”). Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p< 0.10, ** p< 0.05, *** p< 0.01. Worker characteristics is a vector of control variables as described in Table 1 plus industry dummies according to NACE 1-digit classification. Columns (2) and report the sub-sample average values of the job characteristics. Columns (3) and (7) reports the multiplication of the betas from columns (1) and (5) with the sub-sample average values of the characteristics. Columns (4) and (8) report the Shapley values, which describe the absolute contribution of each regressor in the goodness-of-fit of the estimations in column (1) and (5) respectively.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Thomas Bolli: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Filippo Pusterla:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Informed consent

This study uses secondary data without individual identifiers. All authors wrote, read and approved the final manuscript.

Ethical approval

This research uses secondary data and complies with ethical standards.

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Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used deepL write in order to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix

See Tables A.1–A.3.

Table A.2
Sub-sample results: Estimation by executive position.

Dependent variable: effect of working from home on job satisfaction	Non-Executive				Executive			
	(1) $\hat{\beta}_c$	(2) $\tilde{\theta}_c$	(3) $\hat{\beta}_c * \tilde{\theta}_c$	(4) Percentage of Explained Variation	(5) $\hat{\beta}_c$	(6) β_{OLS}	(7) $\hat{\beta}_c * \tilde{\theta}_c$	(8) Percentage of Explained Variation
M1: Working from home worsens the work–life balance	–.190*** (.0227)	2.74	–.52	8.24	–.163*** (.0253)	2.73	–.44	7.14
M2: Working from home enables more flexible forms of working time	.112*** (.0307)	4.26	.48	3.35	.142*** (.0324)	4.14	.59	4.24
M3: Working from home makes my work more interesting	.251*** (.0284)	2.79	.70	12.99	.191*** (.0323)	2.76	.53	10.30
M4: Working from home complicates interaction with colleagues and superiors	–.156*** (.0290)	3.93	–.61	6.04	–.198*** (.0328)	3.94	–.78	7.55
M5: Working from home increases my productivity	.322*** (.0293)	3.50	1.13	15.23	.243*** (.0316)	3.46	.84	11.99
Worker characteristics	Yes			1.77	Yes			3.49
N	1148				845			
R ² (%)	47.62				44.70			
Mean of dependent variable	0.33				0.30			

Notes: Columns (1) and (5) report the results of the OLS regression having as dependent variable the effect of working from home on job satisfaction, which is measured on a Likert scale (–2=“less satisfied”, 0=“no change”, 2=“more satisfied”). Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p< 0.10, ** p< 0.05, *** p< 0.01. Worker characteristics is a vector of control variables as described in Table 1 plus industry dummies according to NACE 1-digit classification. Columns (2) and (6) report the sub-sample average values of the job characteristics. Columns (3) and (7) reports the multiplication of the betas from columns (1) and (5) with the sub-sample average values of the characteristics. Columns (4) and (8) report the Shapley values, which describe the absolute contribution of each regressor in the goodness-of-fit of the estimations in column (1) and (5) respectively.

Table A.3
Sub-sample results: Estimation by age.

Dependent variable: effect of working from home on job satisfaction	Younger (<=35 years)				Older (>35 years)			
	(1) $\hat{\beta}_c$	(2) $\tilde{\theta}_c$	(3) $\hat{\beta}_c * \tilde{\theta}_c$	(4) Percentage of Explained Variation	(5) $\hat{\beta}_c$	(6) β_{OLS}	(7) $\hat{\beta}_c * \tilde{\theta}_c$	(8) Percentage of Explained Variation
M1: Working from home worsens the work–life balance	–.172*** (.0232)	2.75	–.47	7.85	–.179*** (.0243)	2.72	–.49	7.61
M2: Working from home enables more flexible forms of working time	.141*** (.0313)	4.31	.61	4.02	.111*** (.0309)	4.11	.45	3.38
M3: Working from home makes my work more interesting	.246*** (.0315)	2.80	.69	13.37	.189*** (.0293)	2.75	.52	9.97
M4: Working from home complicates interaction with colleagues and superiors	–.159*** (.0294)	3.95	–.63	5.91	–.188*** (.0322)	3.91	–.73	7.33
M5: Working from home increases my productivity	.269*** (.0304)	3.37	.91	12.23	.311*** (.03034)	3.60	1.12	14.69
Worker characteristics	Yes			2.20	Yes			3.17
N	1020				973			
R ² (%)	46.57				46.15			
Mean of dependent variable	0.31				0.32			

Notes: Columns (1) and (5) report the results of the OLS regression having as dependent variable the effect of working from home on job satisfaction, which is measured on a Likert scale (–2=“less satisfied”, 0=“no change”, 2=“more satisfied”). Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p< 0.10, ** p< 0.05, *** p< 0.01. Worker characteristics is a vector of control variables as described in Table 1 plus industry dummies according to NACE 1-digit classification. Columns (2) and (6) report the sub-sample average values of the job characteristics. Columns (3) and (7) reports the multiplication of the betas from columns (1) and (5) with the sub-sample average values of the characteristics. Columns (4) and (8) report the Shapley values, which describe the absolute contribution of each regressor in the goodness-of-fit of the estimations in column (1) and (5) respectively.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

References

Allen, Tammy D., Golden, Timothy D., & Shockley, Kristen M. (2015). How effective is telecommuting? Assessing the status of our scientific findings. *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 16(2), 40–68.

Almeida, Filomena, Rodrigues, Helena, & Freitas, Patrícia (2024). “No Need to Dress to Impress” evidence on teleworking during and after the pandemic: A systematic review. *Administrative Sciences*, 14(4), 76.

Atkin, David, Schoar, Antoinette, & Shinde, Sumit (2023). *Working from home, worker sorting and development: Technical report*, National Bureau of Economic Research.

Bakker, Arnold B., Demerouti, Evangelia, & Sanz-Vergel, Ana (2023). Job demands–resources theory: Ten years later. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 10, 25–53.

Barbieri, Barbara, Balia, Silvia, Sulis, Isabella, Cois, Ester, Cabras, Cristina, Atzara, Sara, & De Simone, Silvia (2021). Dont call it smart: working from home during the pandemic crisis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, Article 741585.

Barbour, Natalia, Menon, Nikhil, & Mannerling, Fred (2021). A statistical assessment of work-from-home participation during different stages of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 11, Article 100441.

Barrero, José María, Bloom, Nicholas, & Davis, Steven J. (2023). The evolution of work from home. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 37(4), 23–49.

Becker, William J., Belkin, Liuba Y., Tuskey, Sarah E., & Conroy, Samantha A. (2022). Surviving remotely: How job control and loneliness during a forced shift to remote work impacted employee work behaviors and well-being. *Human Resource Management*, 61(4), 449–464.

Bellmann, Lutz, & Hübler, Olaf (2020). Working from home, job satisfaction and work–life balance—robust or heterogeneous links? *International Journal of Manpower*.

- Bloom, Nicholas, Han, Ruobing, & Liang, James (2024). Hybrid working from home improves retention without damaging performance. *Nature*, 1–6.
- Bolli, Thomas, & Pusterla, Filippo (2022). Decomposing the effects of digitalization on workers job satisfaction. *International Review of Economics*, 69(2), 263–300.
- Boswell, Wendy R., & Olson-Buchanan, Julie B. (2007). The use of communication technologies after hours: The role of work attitudes and work-life conflict. *Journal of Management*, 33(4), 592–610.
- Brunelle, Eric, & Fortin, Jo-Annie (2021). Distance makes the heart grow fonder: An examination of teleworkers and office workers job satisfaction through the lens of self-determination theory. *Sage Open*, 11(1), Article 2158244020985516.
- Brynjolfsson, Erik, Horton, John J., Ozimek, Adam, Rock, Daniel, Sharma, Garima, & TuYe, Hong-Yi (2020). *COVID-19 and remote work: An early look at US data: Technical report*, National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Camilleri, Mark Anthony (2021). The employees state of mind during COVID-19: A self-determination theory perspective. *Sustainability*, 13(7), 3634.
- Castro-Trancón, Nereida, Zuazua-Vega, Mónica, Osca, Amparo, Cifre, Eva, & García-Izquierdo, Antonio L. (2024). Effects of teleworking on wellbeing from a gender perspective: A systematic review. *Frontiers in Organizational Psychology*, 2, Article 1360373.
- Chung, Heejung, & Van der Lippe, Tanja (2020). Flexible working, work–life balance, and gender equality: Introduction. *Social Indicators Research*, 151(2), 365–381.
- Craig, Lyn, & Churchill, Brendan (2021). Dual-earner parent couples work and care during COVID-19. *Gender, Work & Organization*, 28, 66–79.
- Crawford, Joseph (2022). Working from home, telework, and psychological wellbeing? A systematic review. *Sustainability*, 14(19), 11874.
- Deci, Edward L., Olafsen, Anja H., & Ryan, Richard M. (2017). Self-determination theory in work organizations: The state of a science. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 4, 19–43.
- Deci, Edward L., & Ryan, Richard M. (2012). Self-determination theory. *Handbook of Theories of Social Psychology*, 1(20), 416–436.
- Delanoëije, Joni, Verbruggen, Marijke, & Germeys, Lynn (2019). Boundary role transitions: A day-to-day approach to explain the effects of home-based telework on work-to-home conflict and home-to-work conflict. *Human Relations*, 72(12), 1843–1868.
- Demerouti, Evangelia, Bakker, Arnold B., Nachreiner, Friedhelm, & Schaufeli, Wilmar B. (2001). The job demands-resources model of burnout. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(3), 499.
- Dettmers, Jan, Vahle-Hinz, Tim, Bamberg, Eva, Friedrich, Niklas, & Keller, Monika (2016). Extended work availability and its relation with start-of-day mood and cortisol. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 21(1), 105.
- Emanuel, Natalia, & Harrington, Emma (2023). *Working remotely? Selection, treatment, and the market for remote work: Selection, Treatment, and the Market for Remote Work (June 2023)*. FRB of New York Staff Report, 1061.
- Emanuel, Natalia, Harrington, Emma, & Pallais, Amanda (2023). *The power of proximity to coworkers: training for tomorrow or productivity today?: Technical report*, National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Gajendran, Ravi S., & Harrison, David A. (2007). The good, the bad, and the unknown about telecommuting: meta-analysis of psychological mediators and individual consequences. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92(6), 1524.
- Galanti, Teresa, Guidetti, Gloria, Mazzei, Elisabetta, Zappalà, Salvatore, & Toscano, Ferdinando (2021). Work from home during the COVID-19 outbreak: The impact on employees remote work productivity, engagement, and stress. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 63(7), e426–e432.
- Gallie, Duncan, & Russell, Helen (2009). Work-family conflict and working conditions in Western Europe. *Social Indicators Research*, 93(3), 445–467.
- Gibbs, Michael, Mengel, Friederike, & Siemroth, Christoph (2023). Work from home and productivity: Evidence from personnel and analytics data on information technology professionals. *Journal of Political Economy Microeconomics*, 1(1), 7–41.
- Golden, Timothy D., Veiga, John F., & Dino, Richard N. (2008). The impact of professional isolation on teleworker job performance and turnover intentions: does time spent teleworking, interacting face-to-face, or having access to communication-enhancing technology matter? *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 93(6), 1412.
- Gottlieb, Charles, Grobovsek, Jan, & Poschke, Markus (2020). Working from home across countries. *Covid Economics*.
- Guler, Mehmet Akif, Guler, Kutay, Gulec, Meryem Gunecer, & Ozdoglar, Elif (2021). Working from home during a pandemic: investigation of the impact of COVID-19 on employee health and productivity. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 63(9), 731–741.
- Hackney, Amy, Yung, Marcus, Somasundram, Kumara G., Nowrouzi-Kia, Behdin, Oakman, Jodi, & Yazdani, Amin (2022). Working in the digital economy: A systematic review of the impact of work from home arrangements on personal and organizational performance and productivity. *Plos One*, 17(10), Article e0274728.
- Huettner, Frank, Sunder, Marco, et al. (2012). Axiomatic arguments for decomposing goodness of fit according to Shapley and Owen values. *Electronic Journal of Statistics*, 6, 1239–1250.
- Ipsen, Christine, van Veldhoven, Marc, Kirchner, Kathrin, & Hansen, John Paulin (2021). Six key advantages and disadvantages of working from home in Europe during COVID-19. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(4), 1826.
- Jamal, Mohd Tariq, Alalyani, Wafa Rashid, Thoudam, Prabha, Anwar, Imran, & Bino, Ermal (2021). Telecommuting during COVID 19: a moderated-mediation approach linking job resources to job satisfaction. *Sustainability*, 13(20), 11449.
- Junça Silva, Ana, Violante, Carolina, & Brito, Sílvia (2024). The role of personal and job resources for telework's affective and behavioral outcomes. *Kybernetes*, 53(10), 3754–3773.
- Kelliher, Clare, & Anderson, Deirdre (2010). Doing more with less? Flexible working practices and the intensification of work. *Human Relations*, 63(1), 83–106.
- Kirwan, Emma M., Burns, Annette, O'Suilleabháin, Páiraic S., Summerville, Sarah, McGeehan, Máire, McMahon, Jennifer, Gowda, Ashweeja, & Creaven, Ann-Marie (2024). Loneliness in emerging adulthood: A scoping review. *Adolescent Research Review*, 1–21.
- Kitagawa, Ritsu, Kuroda, Sachiko, Okudaira, Hiroko, & Owan, Hideo (2021). Working from home: Its effects on productivity and mental health. *Covid Economics*, 74, 142–171.
- König, Ronny, & Seifert, Alexander (2022). Digitally savvy at the home office: computer skills of older workers during the COVID-19 pandemic across europe. *Frontiers in Sociology*, 7, Article 858052.
- Kunze, Florian, Hampel, Kilian, & Zimmermann, Sophia (2020). Working from home in the coronavirus crisis: towards a transformation of work environments?.
- Laguerre, Rick A., & Barnes-Farrell, Janet L. (2025). Bringing self-determination theory to the forefront: Examining how human resource practices motivate employees of all ages to succeed. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 40(1), 1–37.
- Lal, Banita, Dwivedi, Yogesh K., & Haag, Markus (2021). Working from home during Covid-19: Doing and managing technology-enabled social interaction with colleagues at a distance. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 1–18.
- Lee, Jong-Wha, Song, Eunbi, et al. (2022). Can older workers stay productive? The role of ICT skills and training. *Journal of Asian Economics*, 79, Article 101438.
- Lund, Susan, Madgavkar, Anu, Manyika, James, & Smit, Sven (2020). Whats next for remote work: An analysis of 2,000 tasks, 800 jobs, and nine countries. *McKinsey Global Institute*, 1–13.
- Lunde, Lars-Kristian, Fløvik, Lise, Christensen, Jan Olav, Johannessen, Håkon A., Finne, Live Bakke, Jørgensen, Ingrid Løken, Mohr, Benedicte, & Vleeshouwers, Jolien (2022). The relationship between telework from home and employee health: a systematic review. *BMC Public Health*, 22(1), 47.
- Lyons, Sean, & Kuron, Lisa (2014). Generational differences in the workplace: A review of the evidence and directions for future research. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 35(S1), S139–S157.
- Magnier-Watanabe, Remy, Benton, Caroline, Orsini, Philippe, Uchida, Toru, & Magnier-Watanabe, Kaoruko (2023). COVID-19 and mandatory teleworking from home in Japan: taking stock to improve satisfaction and job performance. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 31(6), 2252–2279.
- Morganson, Valerie J., Major, Debra A., Oborn, Kurt L., Verive, Jennifer M., & Heelan, Michelle P. (2010). Comparing telework locations and traditional work arrangements: Differences in work-life balance support, job satisfaction, and inclusion. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 25(6), 578–595.
- Morikawa, Masayuki (2022). Work-from-home productivity during the COVID-19 pandemic: Evidence from Japan. *Economic Inquiry*, 60(2), 508–527.
- Morrison, Rachel L. (2009). Are women tending and befriending in the workplace? Gender differences in the relationship between workplace friendships and organizational outcomes. *Sex Roles*, 60, 1–13.
- Nakrošienė, Audronė, Bučiūnienė, Ilona, & Goštautaitė, Bernadeta (2019). Working from home: characteristics and outcomes of telework. *International Journal of Manpower*.
- Oakman, Jodi, Kinsman, Natasha, Stuckey, Rwth, Graham, Melissa, & Weale, Victoria (2020). A rapid review of mental and physical health effects of working at home: how do we optimise health? *BMC Public Health*, 20(1), 1–13.
- Pincus, J. David (1986). Communication satisfaction, job satisfaction, and job performance. *Human Communication Research*, 12(3), 395–419.
- Pluut, Helen, & Wonders, Jaap (2020). Not able to lead a healthy life when you need it the most: Dual role of lifestyle behaviors in the association of blurred work-life boundaries with well-being. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, Article 607294.
- Raziq, Abdul, & Maulabakhsh, Raheela (2015). Impact of working environment on job satisfaction. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 23, 717–725.
- Reuschke, Darja (2019). The subjective well-being of homeworkers across life domains. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 51(6), 1326–1349.
- Russo, Daniel, Hanel, Paul HP, & Van Berkel, Niels (2024). Understanding developers well-being and productivity: a 2-year longitudinal analysis during the covid-19 pandemic. *ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology*, 33(3), 1–44.
- Šakan, Dušana, Žuljević, Dragan, & Rokvić, Nikola (2020). The role of basic psychological needs in well-being during the COVID-19 outbreak: A self-determination theory perspective. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 8, Article 583181.
- Scandura, Terri A., & Lankau, Melenie J. (1997). Relationships of gender, family responsibility and flexible work hours to organizational commitment and job satisfaction. *Journal of Organizational Behavior: The International Journal of Industrial, Occupational and Organizational Psychology and Behavior*, 18(4), 377–391.
- Schade, Hannah M., Digutsch, Jan, Kleinsorge, Thomas, & Fan, Yan (2021). Having to work from home: Basic needs, well-being, and motivation. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(10), 5149.

- Schaufeli, Wilmar B., & Bakker, Arnold B. (2004). Job demands, job resources, and their relationship with burnout and engagement: A multi-sample study. *Journal of Organizational Behavior: The International Journal of Industrial, Occupational and Organizational Psychology and Behavior*, 25(3), 293–315.
- Scheibe, Susanne, Retzlaff, Lena, Hommelhoff, Sabine, & Schmitt, Antje (2024). Age-related differences in the use of boundary management tactics when teleworking: Implications for productivity and work-life balance. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 97(4), 1330–1352.
- Shamsi, Marjan, Iakovleva, Tatiana, Olsen, Espen, & Bagozzi, Richard P (2021). Employees work-related well-being during COVID-19 pandemic: An integrated perspective of technology acceptance model and JD-R theory. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(22), 11888.
- Shapley, Lloyd S. (1953). A value for n-person games. *Contributions to the Theory of Games*, 2(28), 307–317.
- Shockley, Kristen M., Clark, Malissa A., Dodd, Hope, & King, Eden B. (2021). Work-family strategies during COVID-19: Examining gender dynamics among dual-earner couples with young children. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 106(1), 15.
- Singh, Monica Munjial, Amiri, Mohammad, & Sabbarwal, Sherry (2019). Role of job stress on job satisfaction. *International Journal of Management Studies*, 6(4), 57–60.
- Song, Younghwan (2009). Unpaid work at home. *Industrial Relations: A Journal of Economy and Society*, 48(4), 578–588.
- Song, Younghwan, & Gao, Jia (2020). Does telework stress employees out? A study on working at home and subjective well-being for wage/salary workers. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 21(7), 2649–2668.
- Thulin, Eva, Vilhelmson, Bertil, & Johansson, Martina (2019). New telework, time pressure, and time use control in everyday life. *Sustainability*, 11(11), 3067.
- Tudu, Binay, & Singh, Saumya (2023). Conceptualizing the moderating effects between work from home and individual performance—developing a conceptual framework using the self-determination theory. *Current Psychology*, 42(33), 29149–29160.
- Van den Broeck, Anja, Ferris, D. Lance, Chang, Chu-Hsiang, & Rosen, Christopher C. (2016). A review of self-determination theory's basic psychological needs at work. *Journal of Management*, 42(5), 1195–1229.
- Warr, Peter (2003). 20 well-being and the workplace. *Well-Being: Foundations of Hedonic Psychology*, 392.
- Wöhner, Fabienne (2022). Work flexibly, travel less? The impact of telework and flextime on mobility behavior in Switzerland. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 102, Article 103390.
- Wu, Hongyue, & Chen, Yunfeng (2020). The impact of work from home (wfh) on workload and productivity in terms of different tasks and occupations. In *HCI international 2020—late breaking papers: interaction, knowledge and social media: 22nd HCI international conference, HCII 2020, Copenhagen, Denmark, July 19–24, 2020, proceedings 22* (pp. 693–706). Springer.
- Yang, Longqi, Holtz, David, Jaffe, Sonia, Suri, Siddharth, Sinha, Shilpi, Weston, Jeffrey, Joyce, Connor, Shah, Neha, Sherman, Kevin, Hecht, Brent, et al. (2022). The effects of remote work on collaboration among information workers. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 6(1), 43–54.
- Yu, Jun, & Wu, Yihong (2021). The impact of enforced working from home on employee job satisfaction during COVID-19: An event system perspective. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(24), 13207.
- Zacher, Hannes (2014). Individual difference predictors of change in career adaptability over time. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 84(2), 188–198.